

MODERN SOCIETY AND GENDER VALUES

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ANNOTATION

In this article, we review similarities and differences between social and gender norms, reviewing the history of the concepts and identifying key tension points of contrast. We identified six areas of comparison that might be helpful for practitioners working for the promotion of global health as they make sense of social and gender norms. We then offer a definition of gender norms for practitioners and researchers working at the intersection between these two theories. Our definition draws from the two different streams of thought of how norms influence people's actions, acknowledging the double nature of gender norms: beliefs nested in people's minds and embedded in institutions that profoundly affect health-related behaviors and shape differential access to health services.

Keywords. Social norms, gender norms, six areas, global health, health-related behaviors, health services.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada biz ijtimoiy va gender normalari o'rtasidagi o'xshashlik va farqlarni ko'rib chiqamiz, tushunchalar tarixini ko'rib chiqamiz va qarama-qarshilikning asosiy keskinlik nuqtalarini aniqlaymiz. Biz oltita taqqoslash sohasini aniqladik, ular global salomatlikni mustahkamlash uchun ishlaydigan amaliyotchilar uchun foydali bo'lishi mumkin, chunki ular ijtimoiy va gender normalarini tushunishadi. Keyin biz ushbu ikki nazariya kesishmasida ishlaydigan amaliyotchilar va tadqiqotchilar uchun gender normalarining ta'rifini taklif qilamiz. Bizning ta'rifimiz gender me'yorlarining ikki tomonlama tabiatini e'tirof etib, normalarning odamlarning harakatlariga qanday ta'sir qilishiga oid ikki xil fikrlash oqimidan kelib chiqadi: odamlar ongida joylashgan va sog'liqni saqlash bilan bog'liq xatti-harakatlarga chuqur ta'sir ko'rsatadigan va sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlaridan farqli foydalanishni shakllantiradigan muassasalarda o'rnatilgan e'tiqodlar.

Kalit so'zlar. Ijtimoiy me'yorlar, gender me'yorlari, oltita soha, global sog'liqni saqlash, sog'liq bilan bog'liq xatti-harakatlar, sog'liqni saqlash xizmatlari.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой статье мы рассматриваем сходства и различия между социальными и гендерными нормами, анализируя историю концепций и определяя ключевые противоречия. Мы определили шесть областей сравнения, которые могут быть полезны практикующим врачам, работающим над укреплением глобального здравоохранения, поскольку они понимают социальные и гендерные нормы. Затем мы предлагаем определение гендерных норм для практиков и исследователей, работающих на стыке этих двух теорий. Наше определение исходит из двух разных течений мысли о том, как нормы влияют на действия людей, признавая двойную природу гендерных норм: убеждения, заложенные в сознании людей и встроенные в институты, которые глубоко влияют на поведение, связанное со здоровьем, и определяют дифференцированный доступ к услугам здравоохранения.

Ключевые слова. Социальные нормы, гендерные нормы, шесть областей, глобальное здоровье, поведение, связанное со здоровьем, медицинские услуги.

Introduction

In recent years, social norms theory has for the first time been applied in low- and middle-income countries (LMIC) to address a variety of health-related challenges, ranging from adolescent health and female genital cutting, to child marriage and intimate partner violence (Cislaghi and Heise 2019, Gelfand and Jackson 2016, Mackie and Lejeune 2009, Mackie *et al.* 2015). The successful reduction of female genital cutting in Senegal through strategies consistent with social norms theory is a case in point (Mackie 1996, Mackie and Lejeune 2009). Until then, social norm approaches had mostly (albeit not exclusively) been used to reduce unhealthy behaviours in high-income countries, for example, alcohol consumption (Prentice and Miller 1993, Prestwich *et al.* 2016), smoking (Eisenberg and Forster 2003) or use of recreational drugs (Jiloha 2009, Perkins 2003). The introduction of social norms perspectives into health and international development practice helped focus much needed attention on the ‘social’ reasons why individuals do what they do.

The aim of this paper is thus to offer a definition of gender norms for practitioners and researchers working to advance gender equity in health. In the following sections, we look at similarities and differences between traditional conceptualisations of social and gender norms, and at what each field can bring to social improvement efforts. The last section offers a cross-theoretical definition of gender norms.

Social norms

The social sciences have a long-standing fascination with understanding how humans come to work together and, more specifically, how unwritten rules emerge that affect their actions. Interest in social norms is traceable already in Aristotle, Grotius, Hume and Locke, among others. In the 20th century, anthropologists and sociologists spent considerable time and resources studying how attitudes and practices of the group influence attitudes and practices of individuals (Allport 1924, Bovard 1953b, Durkheim 1951, Mackie *et al.* 2015, Parsons and Shils 1951, Schanck 1932, Sherif 1936, Sherif and Cantrill 1947, Sumner 1907, Thibaut and Kelley 1959). Today, the social norms literature has grown varied and multi-faceted (Legros and Cislaghi 2019), with multiple definitions – sometimes contradictory – of what social norms are and how they influence behaviour. Generally speaking, social norms are rules of action shared by people in a given society or group; they define what is considered normal and acceptable behaviour for the members of that group (Cislaghi and Heise 2018a). They can influence, for instance, how people dress for a wedding, stand in line when buying something, shake hands when meeting someone, say ‘bless you’ when someone sneezes, offer their seat on the bus to someone older or speak quietly at the library, to cite a few examples. Three features of social norms theory are important to consider as we look to compare this conceptualisation of norms with that dominant in the gender and women's rights community.

First, much literature on social norms conceptualise norms as separate from (and often opposing to) personal attitudes. While personal attitudes are internally motivated judgements about something (Fishbein and Ajzen 1975), social norms, instead, are beliefs about what other people do and approve of. A personal attitude would be ‘I don't like to smoke’, while a social norm would be ‘My friends expect me to smoke’. The difference is important as some people might want one thing, but are pushed by the norm to do the opposite of what they personally lean towards (Miller and McFarland 1987, Prentice and Miller 1996). Interventions using a

'social norms approach' historically have leveraged the misalignment between (i) people's individual behaviours and attitudes, and (ii) descriptive and injunctive norms (people's perceptions on others' behaviours and attitudes) (Bingenheimer 2019). A case in point is interventions to reduce alcohol use in US campuses. These interventions start with a survey measuring prevalence of behaviours, attitudes and norms. For example, a similar intervention could start by measuring (i) how much students drink and approve of those who drink, and (ii) how much they think other students drink and approve of those who drink. When results show a misalignment between behaviour and norms – for example, (i) 20% drink more than one beer on Saturday night, and (ii) 100% think almost everyone drinks more than one beer on Saturday night – the intervention publicises results with the aim to correct similar harmful misperceptions. To do so, traditionally these interventions bear messages such as: '80% of students in this university drink only one beer on Saturday night' (Berkowitz 2010, Perkins and Berkowitz 1986). Similar interventions have been tested in low- and middle-income countries, where a new stream of action suggests that interventions can first change attitudes of a core group of people, then help them become agents of change in their communities, challenging community members' perceptions of what others in their communities approve of (Cislaghi *et al.* 2019).

Second, various streams in social norms theory posit that norms apply within a 'reference group' (Hornsey *et al.* 2003, Smith *et al.* 2007, Terry *et al.* 2000, White *et al.* 2009). That is, different groups of people have different rules. For instance, a young man may feel reluctant to use foul language in front of his family but feel quite comfortable using coarse language when alone with his friends; he adapts his behaviour to the expectations of specific reference groups. Third, while some scholars have suggested that norms regulate only interdependent actions (Goldstein *et al.* 2012, Lapinski and Rimal 2005, Schmidt and Rakoczy Forthcoming), others argue that they inform independent actions as well (Cislaghi and Heise 2018a, Gelfand *et al.* 2006). Independent actions do not require collaboration with others to be carried out (e.g. brushing your teeth at home). Interdependent actions, instead, require coordination between individuals to achieve one's goal (e.g. organising a marriage ceremony) (Van Lange and Balliet 2015). To date, development interventions explicitly based on norms theory have tended to focus on this latter type of action. In the example of female genital cutting in West Africa, for instance, scholars found that – in certain communities (Shell-Duncan *et al.* 2011) – the cutting was part of a strategy to ensure a daughter's marriageability (Mackie 1996). A mother cannot withdraw her daughter from the tradition of cutting without compromising her daughter's marriage prospects (unless everyone agrees to change the norm of cutting at the same time). Not all theories of norms, however, are exclusively concerned with interdependent actions. Various theories look at how norms influence independent actions, for instance those that focus on socialisation and internalisation of norms (Xenitidou and Edmonds 2014).

Gender norms

The notion of gender norms emerged in the context of larger debates among academics, practitioners and activists around the nature of gender. Gender as a term was popularised in the 1970s by feminists to distinguish those aspects of male and female roles, behaviours and preferences that were socially constructed rather than a function of biology. The goal was to provide a counterpoint to popular perceptions that male female differences were 'natural' and therefore immutable. Feminist sociologists advanced this idea further, arguing that gender is best conceptualised as a social system that apportions resources, roles, power and entitlements

according to whether a person or practice is perceived as male or female, masculine or feminine (Ridgeway and Correll 2004). Most existing gender systems are deeply hierarchical, privileging that which is male or masculine over that which is female or feminine (although this need not be the case) (Heise *et al.* 2019, Weber *et al.* 2019).

Norms are but one element of the gender system, along with gender roles, gender socialisation and gendered power relations. In this account, gender norms are the social rules and expectations that keep the gender system intact. The term *gender norms* first entered the health and development lexicon in the last decade of the 20th century, at a time when several international bodies were making a global commitment to promote gender equality (Connell and Pearse 2014). Most early mentions made reference to ‘gendered power imbalances’ between men and women rather than gender norms. But by 2000, the language of gender norms was on the ascendency in academia, with mentions on google scholar rising from 300 between 1985 and 1990 to 16,700 in the decade between 2000 and 2010. Even though much work on gender norms was directed to promoting women's rights and wellbeing, work on men and masculinity likely contributed to this increased interest in gender norms as a construct, with scholarship emerging on how dominant norms of masculinity can result in harm for both men and women (Connell 1993, Connell and Messerschmidt 2005, Courtenay 2000, Evans *et al.* 2011).

Despite the historical interest of gender scholars and activists on gender norms, theoretical work on gender diversified in the 2010s, with the rise of queer studies and transgender activism. Discourse on gender norms and gender as a social system began to coexist with competing understandings of gender as a deeply held psychological sense of oneself as either a man, a woman or something in between. Popular use of the term also changed, as people began to substitute the word gender for sex, losing the important distinction between biology and social construction. While reviewing the entirety of this literature is beyond the scope of this article, Heise *et al.* (2019) recently reviewed how understandings of how gender have diversified over time, with implications for efforts to increase people's health.

Four core features in the gender norms discourse are relevant for this paper. The first is that gender norms are learned in childhood, from parents and peers, in a process commonly known as socialisation (Bem 1981, Tenenbaum and Leaper 2002) and then reinforced (or contested) in family and the larger social context: through school, the workplace, religion, the media, and other social institutions. The second is that inequitable gender norms reflect and perpetuate inequitable power relations that are often disadvantageous to women (Connell 2014, Lazar 2005). The third contribution of gender theory is the observation that gender norms are embedded in and reproduced through institutions. Policies and regulations, decision-making processes and biases embodied in how institutions function are a function of a given gender system and reinforce gender norms in the population whose lives intersect with those institutions. Finally, gender norms are produced and reproduced through social interaction, as individuals engage in practices that signify, align or contest various notions of masculinity or maleness and femininity or femaleness (West and Zimmerman 1987).

Key differences between social and gender norms

Social theorists, including anthropologists, sociologists and feminist scholars, tends to conceptualise norms as rules of behaviour at the level of society and institutions (Allport 1933, Durkheim 1951, Parsons and Shils 1951, Pearse and Connell 2015). We find it useful to define this conceptualisation of gender norms as existing in the world *outside* of the individual; they

are present when a boy or girl is born, in the world around them. Through various social mechanisms (including socialisation in the family, the media and engagement with institutions), gender norms are enforced, learnt and internalised (Hyde 2014). By contrast, other disciplines, such as social psychology, philosophy and behavioural economics, have tended to define social norms as people's beliefs about what is in the mind of others (Chalub *et al.* 2006, Gintis 2010, Halbesleben *et al.* 2005). Norms thus, in this tradition, exist *inside* the mind. Both approaches include the understanding that the mind and the world influence each other, but each tends to privilege one perspective over the other in their study of norms.

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